

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

MAPWORMS MICRO-CT IMAGING PROTOCOLS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction.....	4
2 METHODOLOGY.....	4
2.1 Equipment	4
3 Scanning protocols for <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i>	4
3.1 Sample Preparation	4
3.2 Scanning Procedure.....	4
4 Scanning protocols for <i>Glycera tridactyla</i>	6
4.1 Sample Preparation	6
4.2 Scanning Procedure.....	6
REFERENCES.....	8

1 INTRODUCTION

MAPWORMS project aims to propose robots that are inspired by simplified forms of marine Annelida, able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli, thus adapting to the working environment with a shape-morphing strategy with unique features in terms of powering and eco-friendliness. In this framework, by deepening the knowledge on taxonomy, behavior and ecology of Annelida, micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) was used to provide the morphological and anatomical description of annelids. This document includes the establishment of the appropriate scanning protocols for the visualisation of external and internal structures of two selected annelids and specifically of the *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni* (Sipuncula) and *Glycera tridactyla* (Polychaeta) specimens which have been selected as model species for the creation of the bio-inspired robot.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 EQUIPMENT

All micro-CT scans were performed with a SkyScan 1172 micro-tomograph (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) at the Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR). This micro-CT scanner uses a tungsten source and is equipped with an 11MP CCD camera (4000 x 2672 pixels), which can reach a maximal resolution of $< 0.8 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$.

3 SCANNING PROTOCOLS FOR *PHASCOLOSOMA (PHASCOLOSOMA) STEPHENSONI*

3.1 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Phascololoma's specimens were fixed in 4% formalin for one week and subsequently were washed with distilled water in order to remove the remaining formalin. Specimens were dehydrated in a graded series of ethanol solutions (20%, 50%, 70%) up to 96% within 24 hours in each solution and stored in 96% ethanol. In order to increase the tissue contrast, specimens were stained with 1% iodine dissolved in 96% ethanol modifying the staining protocol presented in Metscher (2009).

3.2 SCANNING PROCEDURE

Sipuncula specimens were scanned at a voltage of 60kV and a current of 167 μA without filter for a full rotation of 360°. Images were acquired at a pixel size of around 4.83 μm with a camera binning of 1x1. Exposure time was 318 ms and a frame averaging was set at 3. Projection images were reconstructed into cross-section images (Figure 1) using SkyScan's NRecon software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) which employs a modified Feldkamp's back-projection algorithm. Scans were reconstructed in a range of attenuation coefficients of 0 - 0.29, with a beam-hardening correction of 59%, smoothing of 2, and ring artifact correction of 20. The reconstructed images were stored as 16-bit TIFF images. Volume renderings of each specimen (Figure 2) were created using the CTBox software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium).

Figure 1 Cross section images of a *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni* specimen

Figure 2 Volume rendering of a *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni* specimen

4 SCANNING PROTOCOLS FOR GLYCERA TRIDACTYLA

4.1 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Glycera's specimens were fixed in 4% formalin for one week and subsequently were washed with distilled water in order to remove the remaining formalin. Specimens were dehydrated in a graded series of ethanol solutions (20%, 50%) up to 70% within 24 hours in each solution and stored in 70% ethanol. Specimens were firstly scanned without any contrast agent in order to visualise the jaws and then they were embedded into 0.3% PTA dissolved in 70% ethanol (Metscher 2009) in order to visualise the pharyngeal anatomy.

4.2 SCANNING PROCEDURE

For the unstained samples, polychaeta specimens were scanned at a voltage of 50-60kV and a current of 167-199 μ A without filter for a full rotation of 360°. Images were acquired at a pixel size of around 3.5-4.7 μ m with a camera binning of 1 \times 1. For the stained samples, polychaeta specimens were scanned at a voltage of 60kV and a current of 167 μ A without filter for a full rotation of 360°. Images were acquired at a pixel size of around 3-4.14 μ m with a camera binning of 1 \times 1. Exposure time was 315-318 ms and a frame averaging was set at 3.

Projection images were reconstructed into cross-section images (Figure 3) using SkyScan's NRecon software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) which employs a modified Feldkamp's back-projection algorithm. Scans were reconstructed in a range of attenuation coefficients of 0 - 0.21 for the unstained and 0-0.6 for the stained specimens, with a beam-hardening correction of 59%, smoothing of 2, and ring artifact correction of 20. The reconstructed images were stored as 16-bit TIFF images. Volume renderings of each specimen (Figure 4) were created using the CTVox software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium).

Figure 3 Cross section images of a *Glycera tridactyla* specimen

Figure 4 Volume rendering of A) an unstained and B) a stained *Glycera tridactyla* specimen

REFERENCES

Metscher, B.D. (2009). MicroCT for comparative morphology: Simple staining methods allow high-contrast 3D imaging of diverse non-mineralized animal tissues. *BMC Physiology* 9, 11.